

CULTIVATE PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

SERIOUS GAMES FOR CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT IN FOOD SHARING

Food sharing offers numerous social, economic, and environmental benefits. To make these benefits more accessible, we research, test, and co-create **tools and games that can support citizen engagement and social inclusion in food sharing initiatives**. These are collected in the **Library of Citizen Engagement**. In the city of Utrecht we have co-created serious games with food sharing initiatives (FSIs) to stimulate citizen engagement in food sharing. The games support citizen engagement by helping people connect and learn from one another and have a good time while learning about topics such as **growing together, cooking and eating together**, and the **prevention and redistribution of food waste**. Four serious game prototypes were designed. “Oma komt’s eraan” is a children’s game about foraging and composting in an edible neighborhood. “Let’s Eat” is a game about the edible neighbourhood of Rijnvliet. “Common Ground” has been co-designed and tested with urban gardening initiatives. And the “Futures of Food Sharing” card deck game is growing with the CULTIVATE project. Practitioners can use these games to engage with citizens and find new volunteers or interested parties to work with. For example, “Future of Food Sharing”, can be used with policy makers to create better futures for food sharing, while “Common Ground” gives players a sense of what it means to build and maintain an urban garden, teaching players about the challenges they will encounter in real life. In “Let’s Eat” players learn about the edible wild plants growing in Rijnvliet, as well as harvesting, cooking, preservation, and maintenance. All of the games bring people together, who may not have come together otherwise. **The games will be available for print and play** through the Library of Citizen Engagement, and can be played in public, private, and community settings. We do recommend using them in combination with other citizen engagement tools, with dedicated community space, and a game host or facilitator.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Future actions will be the replication of the games for spoke cities of the consortium CULTIVATE.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

Library of Citizen Engagement: libraryofcitizenengagement.softtr.app/

Three Serious Game Prototypes: zenodo.org/records/11395667

Library of Citizen Engagement: Citizen Engagement with Food Sharing and Resilience: zenodo.org/records/15260766

Txell Blanco, from Wageningen University, presenting “Let’s Eat” game

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